

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER PREFERENCE IN TATA PUNCH VARIANTS

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Abstract: *Customer preference is an essential step towards understanding the consumer choice, behavior, likes and dislikes and has therefore always received a great attention from marketers, however the study on customer preference towards tata punch variant's objective is to understand the customer satisfaction level and even aims to understand the factors affecting the customer selection towards tata punch. The research methodology includes primary data collection with the help of convenient sampling method, this report also has the data analysis with the different tests like chi square test, ranking analysis. Research has shown that customers are satisfied with Tata Punch and the main reason why they are attracted to Tata Punch is its features, safety, brand image and price of this model.*

Key words : Tata punch, customers satisfaction, customer preference, factor effects

Introduction

Tata punch is a subcompact by Tata motors cars, since 2021. Tata punch is positioned as the smallest SUV of the brand under the model of Tata Nexon. Tata punch was launched in India on 18 October 2021. The Tata punch will be available in four trim levels pure ex-show room price 5,664,900, adventure ex-show room price 6,49,900, accomplished ex-show room price 7,39,900, creative ex-show room price 8,38,900. Tata offers the punch in a total of 7 colors. The top variant gets a dual tone finish with a black roof, but it gets a white roof with the red and blue paint options. Tata punch occupies the topmost list of the safest cars in the Indian car market with higher score of 16.453 points with five stars for adult's occupant and 40.891 points with four stars for children occupant protection this rating was given by Global NCAP car safety agency. The main purpose of this research is to know people's opinion on Tata punch, which is newly launched under Tata Motors. to know the reasons that motivate customers to purchase Tata Punch and whether the customer is satisfied with the features offered in this car.

Objective of the study

The following are the objectives of the study

To understand the satisfaction of the customers towards Tata punch variants

To know the factor affecting customer selection towards Tata punch variants

Scope of the study

The study is focusing on the factor which affecting the customers to buy this car and the reason behind its purchase and to know whether the customers are satisfied with its special offers at affordable price.

Limitation of the study

The following are the limitations of the study

The study is limited to 50 members only

The primary data was collected in Kropex Tata motors, Singasandra

Time duration of study is December 2021 to January 2022

Literature review

Nainesh Patel and Prinsa Patel (2020): - Descriptive research with primary and secondary data collection. The sample size for this research is 160 data analysis tools are frequency distribution and T-test. The above study shows that the large number of respondents is preferring Tata nexon due to its features, mileage, price, good design and quality service. Dr. Swati Singh and Manoj Joshi (2015): - The research entails a mixed method research comprising of case study and empirical survey the findings reveal that corporate brand equity an esthetic value for money and reliability are the major attribute of tata nano that makes it attractive for its targeted customer.

Dr. Sandesh Kumar Sharma, Kiran Sharma and Makshud Khan (2011): - convenient sampling is used to collect data. Sampling size is 100. Both primary and secondary data are used in research data collection. The main purpose of this research is to understand the customer level of satisfaction towards Tata motors. Finally, in concluded Tata cars are people's car as it is satisfactory on all parameters.

Research methodology and tools

For this study the Primary data has been collected directly through customers in kropex Tata motors Singasandra. Questionnaires are prepared according to the research topic. In such a way the sample respondents are selected by using convenience sampling method. The sample size of the research is 50. Secondary data is consisted of literature review and company

profile. 4-point Likert scale, chi square test and ranking analysis are used as tools to analyse the data.

Findings

Socioeconomic characteristic may influence the satisfaction level of the customers. In order to find out the relationship between Socioeconomic characteristic and satisfaction level. The following statistical analysis has been made on the basis of following null hypothesis.

Ho: satisfaction level and socioeconomic characteristics has no relationship.

Satisfaction level and socio economic characteristic

Analyzing the relationship between socio economic characteristics and satisfaction level

Occupation and Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level

Occupation place important role while purchase of any new product. Based on occupation people have different knowledge and experience. To know the relationship between customer satisfaction level and occupation the following Chi-square test has been done. Table 1 and Chart 1 shows the relationship between Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and occupation

Table 1: Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and occupation: χ^2 test

Satisfaction level	Occupation			Total
	Student	Employee	Self-employee	
Satisfied	01	07	05	13
Not satisfied	08	19	10	37
Total	09	26	15	50

$\chi^2 = 1.467$ Degree of freedom = 2 Table value = 5.991

Ho: Satisfaction level and the occupation of the responded has no relationship.

Ha: Satisfaction level and the occupation of responded has relationship.

The calculated value of χ^2 1.467 is less than table value 5.991. It means the null hypothesis is accepted, and alternative hypothesis is rejected which means there is no relationship between Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and occupation

Gender and Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level

Female and male will have different of opinions, tastes, nature and character. So, to know the satisfaction level of the gender following chi-square test has been conducted. Table 2 and Chart 2 shows the relationship between Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and gender.

Table 2:Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and gender: χ^2 test

Satisfaction level	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Satisfied	05	08	13
Not satisfied	20	17	37
Total	25	25	50

$\chi^2 = 0.936$ Degree of freedom = 1 Table Value = 3.841

Ho: Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and the gender of the responded has no relationship.

Ha: Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and the gender of the responded has relationship.

The calculated χ^2 value 0.936 is less than table value 3.841. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted, and alternative hypothesis is rejected which means there is no relationship between Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and gender.

Age and Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level

Different age group of people will have different opinions some features and technologies will attract the different age group people. If one feature attract the young age group that will not attract the old age people so to the satisfaction level of different age group the following chi-square test has been conducted. Table 3 and Chart 3 shows the relationship between Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and age.

Table 3: Tata Punch customer satisfaction level and age: χ^2 test

Satisfaction level	Age				Total
	18-24	25-30	31-35	Above35	
Satisfied	05	04	01	03	13
Not satisfied	19	08	05	05	37
Total	24	12	06	08	50

$\chi^2 = 1.489$ Degree of freedom = 3 Table value = 7.815

Ho: Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and the age of the responded has no relationship.

Ha: Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and the age of the responded has relationship.

The calculated χ^2 value 1.489 is less than table value 7.815. It means the null hypothesis is accepted, and alternative hypothesis is rejected which means there is no relationship between Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and age.

Income and Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level

If the person earns more money, the buying or purchasing capacity will also increase on the other hand if the person earns less the buying or purchasing capacity is less. So to know weather TATA Punch variant customers are satisfied or not with its cost and features based on their income, to test the relationship between TATA Punch variants customer satisfaction level and income the following Chi-square test has been conducted. Table 4 and Chart 4 show the relationship between TATA Punch variants customer satisfaction level and income.

Table 4: Tata Punch variants customer satisfaction level and income. χ^2 test

Satisfaction level	Income				Total
	Below 25000	25001-35000	35001-50000	50000 Above	
Satisfied	12	01	00	00	13
Not satisfied	27	07	01	02	37
Total	39	08	01	02	50

$\chi^2 = 2.273$ Degree of freedom=3 Table Value=7.815

Ho: Satisfaction level and the income of the responded has no relationship.

Ha: Satisfaction level and the income of the responded has relationship.

The calculated χ^2 value 2.273 is less than table value 7.815. It means the null hypothesis is accepted, and alternative hypothesis is rejected which means there is no relationship between satisfaction level and Income.

Factors effecting customer selection to wards Tata Punch variants

If the customers want to buy any products, they will verify so many things like brand, design, colors, quality, quantity, guarantee, style, and so many other things. Some time they ask their friends, relatives or experts' opinion to purchase any new car. To know which factor is affecting the customers to buy this TATA Punch variants the following ranking analysis has been conducted. Table 5 and Chart 5 represent the ranking analysis of factors affecting customer selection towards TATA Punch variants.

Table 5: Factors affecting customer selection towards TATA Punch variants:

Ranking Analysis

Sl.no	Factors/Rank	1	2	3	4	5	Total
1	Brand	34 (170)	7 (28)	9 (27)	00 (00)	00 (00)	50 (225)
2	Price	20 (100)	18 (72)	11 (33)	01 (02)	00 (00)	50 (207)
3	Styling	27 (175)	13 (52)	09 (27)	01 (02)	00 (00)	50 (256)
4	Fuel economy or milage	25 (125)	16 (64)	08 (24)	01 (02)	00 (00)	50 (215)
5	Space	21 (105)	18 (72)	09 (27)	02 (04)	00 (00)	50 (208)
6	Comfort	30 (150)	14 (56)	06 (18)	00 (00)	00 (00)	50 (224)
7	Safety	30 (130)	11 (44)	09 (27)	00 (00)	00 (00)	50 (201)
8	Features	24 (120)	15 (60)	11 (33)	00 (00)	00 (00)	50 (213)
9	Ground clearance	26 (130)	13 (52)	10 (30)	01 (02)	00 (00)	50 (214)
10	After sales and service cost	21 (105)	19 (76)	08 (24)	02 (04)	00 (00)	50 (209)
11	Resale value	23 (115)	15 (60)	12 (36)	00 (00)	00 (00)	50 (211)
12	Family requirement	29 (145)	14 (56)	06 (18)	01 (02)	00 (00)	50 (221)
13	Quality of the product	28 (140)	14 (56)	07 (21)	01 (02)	00 (00)	50 (219)
14	Colors	24 (120)	18 (56)	08 (24)	00 (00)	00 (00)	50 (200)
15	Performance	24 (120)	19 (76)	06 (24)	01 (02)	00 (00)	50 (222)

(Figures in the cells denotes number of respondents. Figures in the parenthesis denotes score)

Table 5 and Chart 5 represent the factors affecting customer selection towards TATA Punch Variants. The ranks were assigned as follows.

1. Styling
2. Brand
3. Comfort
4. Performance
5. Family requirement
6. Quality of the product
7. Fuel economy or milage
8. Ground clearance
9. Features
10. Resale value
11. After sale and service cost
12. Space
13. Price
14. Safety
15. Color

From the above analysis it can be concluded that, the main factor which affect the customer preference is 'styling' because of its design it scores more points (256). The second factor is

'Brand' TATA group has retained the title of India's most valuable and trustworthy brand it scores (225) points. The third factor is 'comfort' it scores (224) points because of its improvised rear seats and legroom are spacious. Fourth affective factor is 'Performance' it scores (222) points. The fifth factor is 'Family requirement' to buy any product meeting the requirement of family is very important it scores (221) points. The sixth factor which affect the customer is 'Quality of the product' without quality the customer will not buy the cars, so it scores (219) points. The seventh factor is 'fuel economy or milage' TATA Punch provides a milage of 19km/l so its scores (215) points. The eight factor is 'Ground clearance' the ground clearance in TATA Punch is 187mm because of this it scores (214) points. The ninth factor is the attractive 'Features' which are afford in TATA punch it scores (213) points. The tenth factor is 'Resale value' everyone is thinking that TATA punch will give more resale value in future because of that only there are ready to purchase the car, so it scores (211) points. The eleventh factor is 'After sales and service cost' it scores (209) points. The twelfth factor is 'Space' with the limited spaces TATA Punch provided all the requirements of the customer so that it scores (208). The thirteenth factor is 'Price' with low price it provides lots of features because of this customer are attracting towards TATA punch so it scores (207) points. The fourteenth factor is 'Safety' while purchasing the car most of them are concern about the safety so that it scores (201) points. the last factor is 'Color' it scores (200) points. These are the various factors which affects customer while selecting the car.

Conclusion

A study on customer preference in Tata Punch variants research was conducted under the premises of Kropex Tata motors, Singasandra. 50 respondents were targeted.. The main aim of the study is to know the customer satisfaction level and factors affecting customers selection towards Tata Punch variants. It was concluded that 13 persons are satisfied with Tata Punch variants features, price, and its colors, 37 persons are not satisfied with Tata Punch variants. Styling, brand, comfort, performance, family requirements are the main factor which influencing the customers to buy this Tata Punch variants. It is found that the large number of respondents is preferring Tata Punch due to its fuel economy or milage, ground clearance, price and safety . after all the research Tata motors is an overall strong company that has found it's strength and expansion through it's parent company. in conclude Tata punch is indeed a good choice for customer who need a particular comfortable SUV especially for the price that it is offered at.

Reference

1. <http://auto.hindustantimes.com/auto/cars/what-makes-tata-punch-suv-the-safest-car-on-indian-roads-know-here-41634539571864.html>
2. http://www.researchgate.net/publication/318124494_New_Market_Creation_via_Innovation_A_Study_on_Tata_Nano_
3. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Tata-Group>
4. Naisha Patel, Prinsa Patel “ A study on customer Perception towards TATA Nexon Car in bardoli City”.(2020)
5. <https://studycorgi.com/tata-motors-company-market-research/>